

FLAASH and MODTRAN4: State-of-the-Art Atmospheric Correction for Hyperspectral Data

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Abstract—FLAASH (Fast Line-of-sight Atmospheric Analysis of Spectral Hypercubes) is a MODTRAN-based "atmospheric correction" software package which is being developed by the Air Force Research Laboratory, Hanscom AFB, and Spectral Sciences, Inc., to support current and planned SWIR/visible/UV hyperspectral and multispectral sensors, typically in image format. The AF intent is to provide surface reflectance and emissivity image cubes of sufficient accuracy for input into subsequent analyses of surface properties, effectively removing the atmospheric component. The main objectives are (1) accurate, physics-based descriptions of surface and atmospheric properties (such as surface albedo, relative elevation, water vapor column, aerosol and cloud optical properties, and temperatures), (2) minimal computational time requirements, and (3) interactive, user-friendly interface for generating MODTRAN4-based look-up tables. Validation and development exercises are being carried out on data from the airborne AVIRIS and HYDICE sensors, which cover the 0.4-2.5 μm region; applications are also planned for infrared sensors. The algorithms for deriving the surface and atmospheric properties utilize the full MODTRAN4 accuracy (thermal and solar) and account for adjacency effects associated with atmospheric scattering. A new line-tail treatment and a correlated- k (CK) radiative transfer algorithm[1,2] provide improved accuracy, especially under conditions of partial cloud cover and/or heavy aerosol loading.

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1. INTRODUCTION: MODTRAN AND FLAASH

The MODTRAN band model accurately and efficiently calculates the scattering and absorption signatures of realistic molecular, aerosol and cloudy environments in the lower and middle atmosphere. The new $\frac{1}{4} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ line tail treatment greatly reduces residuals between MODTRAN and benchmark line-by-line transmitted solar irradiances in the H_2O and O_2 short-wave IR bands. The MODTRAN4 Correlated- k option introduces Beer's Law into the band model and eliminates Curtis-Godson averaging. CK also leads to a more accurate treatment of multiple scattering, with well defined layer optical depths and single scattering albedos; however, the standard MODTRAN band model radiance predictions in the down-looking hyperspectral imaging scenario agree well with the CK results and require considerably less computation time. MODTRAN4 also includes, in addition to the standard 1 cm^{-1} band model data file, a new 15 cm^{-1} version to speed up short wave calculations. The 15 cm^{-1} version has not yet been optimized for accuracy, however.

Validation is provided through two avenues. The first involves direct comparisons with line-by-line calculations, as exemplified by FASE (FASCODE for the Environment)[3], the line-by-line algorithm jointly developed from FASCODE (Fast Atmospheric Signature Code)[4] by DoD and DOE. The FASE radiation transport is based on an optimized line-shape decomposition algorithm[5] and provides the molecular standard for layer effective optical depths, single scattering albedos, and transmittances. This enables the MODTRAN4 algorithm to be refined for more flexible spectral resolution plus efficient and accurate determination of those layer quantities necessary for multiple scattering algorithms; e.g. DISORT[6]. The second validation step centers on comparisons against a variety of measurements, some of which are airborne visible and IR up-welling radiances, including both clear and clouded skies.

FLAASH incorporates new and existing hyperspectral analysis methods that have been developed for both research and general use[7-11]. It is designed as a general-purpose

atmospheric correction and data simulation code and is evolving in parallel with upgrades to MODTRAN in order to take advantage of the latest improvements in accuracy and speed.

The initial version of FLAASH provides:

- An analysis tool to support AVIRIS, HYDICE, and similar SWIR/visible/UV imaging sensors;
- A graphical user interface for performing MODTRAN4 spectral calculations, which include creating the essential look-up tables for atmospheric correction, property retrieval, and data simulation.

On output FLAASH provides:

- Data-derived column water vapor and relative surface elevation (e.g., from column oxygen) maps;
- Aerosol amounts (visibility values) derived from objects in the scene having known reflectances;
- Atmospherically corrected images (i.e., surface spectral reflectance cubes, with the H₂O, other absorption bands, and aerosol scattering removed) for non-thermal wavelengths (SWIR through UV), including an image-sharpening 'adjacency' effect correction.

FLAASH can also output simulated radiance data for a given sensing geometry, atmospheric condition, and input reflectance image.

FLAASH Methodology

As in other first-principles atmospheric correction codes, model simulations of the spectral radiance are performed for appropriate atmospheric and viewing conditions over a range of surface reflectances. The desired properties (reflectance, column water vapor, etc.) are derived from the spectral radiance at each image pixel using look-up tables that are generated from these simulations. To minimize the number of simulations (i.e., MODTRAN runs) required to generate the tables, a physics-based parameterization of the radiance-reflectance relationship is used. This relationship can vary across the scene due to variations in water vapor column density. Therefore, as in the ATREM code[8] the water vapor column is first determined for each pixel, then the result is used as an input to the surface reflectance retrieval algorithm.

The initial version of FLAASH handles the SWIR through UV wavelengths where thermal emission can be neglected. For this situation the spectral radiance L^* at a sensor pixel may be parameterized as[12-14].

$$L^* = Ap/(1-\rho_e S) + B\rho_e/(1-\rho_e S) + L^*_a \quad (1)$$

where ρ is the pixel surface reflectance, ρ_e is an average surface reflectance for the surrounding region, S is the spherical albedo of the atmosphere (i.e., the atmospheric reflectance for upwelling radiation), L^*_a is the radiance

back-scattered by the atmosphere, and A and B are coefficients that depend on atmospheric and geometric conditions. The first term in Equation (1) corresponds to the radiance from the surface that travels directly into the sensor, while the second term corresponds to the radiance from the surface that is scattered by the atmosphere into the sensor.

The values of A , B , S , and L^*_a are determined empirically from MODTRAN spectral radiance calculations for three different spatially and spectrally uniform reflectances ($\rho=\rho_e=0, 0.5, \text{ and } 1.0$). The backscattered radiance term L^*_a is simply the radiance for zero surface reflectance ($\rho=\rho_e=0$). The first (direct radiance) term is output by MODTRAN separately from the total radiance L^* ; thus, the second (scattered radiance) term is isolated by subtracting the direct surface radiance and L^*_a from the total radiance. Equation (1) applies rigorously to monochromatic light. However, because S is small (of order 10^{-2} to 10^{-1} for clear sky) the radiance-reflectance relationship is sufficiently linear that Equation (1) accurately describes integrated in-band (i.e., sensor channel) radiances as well as true monochromatic radiance.

The spatially averaged reflectance ρ_e is used to account for "adjacency effects"--i.e., radiance contributions that, because of atmospheric scattering, originate from parts of the surface not in the direct line of sight. Strictly speaking, the ρ_e 's in the numerator of the second term and in the denominators of the first and second terms are not identical.

The former represents a weighted average over the surface region (typically around 1 km in diameter when viewed from a high-altitude sensor) that contributes to forward scattering from the ground into the sensor. The latter represents an average over a larger region that contributes to the scattering back down to the ground. However, because S is small and the size of the averaging region is non-critical, the two averaged reflectances may be equated with little error.

The method for solving Equation (1) for the surface reflectance ρ in FLAASH parallels that in the ATCOR2 code[10] but differs in detail. MODTRAN4 spectral radiance calculations for surface reflectances of 0, 0.5, and 1.0 are performed for a range of water vapor column densities to determine the Equation (1) parameters as a function of wavelength and water vapor column. The parameters for a spectral interval containing a selected water band are used to determine water vapor column densities for each pixel. The method involves comparisons of data and simulations for in-band and out-of-band radiance averages using a 2-dimensional look-up table.

In addition to determining the water vapor column density, FLAASH derives pressure elevations by applying the same method to a uniformly mixed gas species absorption band. Because MODTRAN4 more accurately represents molecular absorption, the species column densities derived from FLAASH are expected to be more accurate than those obtained using previous versions of MODTRAN as well as from more approximate radiation transfer algorithms. Several bands of O₂ and CO₂ are currently being examined

for best accuracy in elevation definition across the image. Considerations include the sensitivity to sensor signal-to-noise, systematic errors, and the type of surface terrain.

2. RESULTS

A number of hyperspectral images from the NASA/JPL AVIRIS sensor[15] and the USAF HYDICE sensor[16] have been analyzed to test the initial FLAASH code. Water vapor and O₂ band derived elevation images are shown to be strongly correlated (Figure 1); the lowest water vapor columns generally occur coincident with the highest elevations. As the O₂ band actually measures air pressure, the absolute elevations are sensitive to the local weather conditions. For relative elevations the main source of error is spectral non-linearity of the reflectance in the O₂ band region, which varies with the type of terrain and is especially pronounced with vegetation. Better accuracy will be obtained in the future by developing a background-subtraction or terrain-dependent correction procedure or shifting to alternate O₂ or CO₂ bands.

The importance of adjacency correction and cloud identification is also emerging from analyses of AVIRIS and HYDICE data cubes. Reflectance spectra generated using the full method described in the previous section differ significantly from the reflectance generated without accounting for adjacency effects; this is especially noticeable, for example, when flat calibration panels have been placed over green grass (Figure 2). The adjacency correction effect is also seen in heightened image contrast (Figure 3).

Additional HYDICE measurements of scenes containing spectrally calibrated fiducials (e.g. panels) as well as AVIRIS scenes containing well-characterized terrain are now being analyzed. Comparisons of retrieved and known surface reflectances are very useful for inferring aerosol properties, which are the major source of uncertainty in visible and UV surface reflectance retrievals for clear-sky conditions. Either calibrated panels or "dark" pixels (known to contain vegetation or water) can be compared with retrieved reflectances as an aerosol optical property is varied, leading to a best fit. Aerosol properties that may be retrieved include the optical depth, scattering albedo, and possibly the scattering phase function.

Quantitative comparisons of FLAASH retrievals with results from other algorithms and with "ground truth" measurements are complicated by many factors, including sensor radiance and wavelength calibration uncertainties, uncertainties in the state of the atmosphere, approximations in the atmospheric radiative transfer modeling, and "ground truth" uncertainties; most of these are functions of the scene and sensor. Validation efforts are ongoing and will be discussed in a future paper.

Figure 1 (Top) AVIRIS Cuprite, NE scene. (Middle) Retrieved column water vapor map (darker areas denote lower water content). (Bottom) Retrieved elevation map from the 762 nm O₂ band (darker areas denote higher elevation).

Figure 2 Effect of adjacency correction on retrieved spectra of nominal 2%, 16%, and 32% gray calibration panels.

Figure 3 AVIRIS Moffett Field scene reflectance without (left) and with (right) adjacency correction.

3. CONCLUSIONS

Development of FLAASH, a fast software package for atmospheric correction and modeling of hyperspectral images using MODTRAN4, has begun with a focus on sensors covering SWIR through UV wavelengths. An initial version of the code has been developed for analysis of AVIRIS and HYDICE data. Future efforts will focus on accuracy evaluations, improvements to MODTRAN4, access to a comprehensive library of reflectance spectra, incorporation of aerosol retrieval techniques, and extensions of FLAASH to additional sensors and to the thermal IR region.

4. ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

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6. BIOGRAPHIES

Gail P. Anderson, Air Force Research Lab (AFRL), is the lead scientist for the development of background atmospheric radiative transfer codes, including MODTRAN and FASCODE. This work was initiated by a team of AFRL or AFGL scientists 20 years ago. MODTRAN is now the product of a team consisting primarily of the authors of this paper, particularly Dr. Alexander Berk of Spectral Sciences, Inc., with other contributions from within the commercial and government sectors, including significant work by the Navy and Army. The development of FLAASH (see text) was initiated by Dr. Laila Jeong at AFRL, with Dr. Steven Adler-Golden as the SSI lead. Ms. Anderson's background includes degrees from UC Santa Barbara and University of Colorado, where she worked for both LASP and NCAR. She was also the recipient of an Air